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PHYSICAL REALITY IN COLLOID PHYSICS OF GEL OXYHYDRATES

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Annotation: The paper makes far-reaching assumptions about the quantum-colloid representation of matter as a macrosystem: a microscopic entangled system becomes a boundary macroscopic (for example) oxyhydrate system, that is, a special quantum form of composite correlations, that is, electro-magnetic noise entangled states (entangledstates) of cluster colloid systems.

The entanglement of oxyhydrate systems is a special quantum form of correlations of composite systems that does not have a classical analogue. It occurs in a system consisting of two or more interacting subsystems (or interacting previously and then separated), and is a superposition of macroscopically different States. In this case, fluctuations of individual parts are interconnected, but not through classical interactions (correlations), but through non-local quantum correlations.

An experimental method is proposed for estimating the size of third clusters of oxyhydrate systems in a dispersion medium, considering entanglement as a special quantum form of correlations of composite systems that does not have a classical analogue. It occurs in a system consisting of two or more interacting subsystems and is a superposition of macroscopically different States. In this case, fluctuations of individual parts are interconnected, but not through classical interactions (correlations), but through non-local quantum correlations.

Keywords: lagrangian maps, oxyhydrate systems, colloid clusters, spontaneous pulsation current, spike surge, diffuse double electric layer,

dissociation disproportion destruction of macromolecules, Whitney theory, geometry of caustics

ФИЗИЧЕСКАЯ РЕАЛЬНОСТЬ В КОЛЛОИДНОЙ ФИЗИКЕ ГЕЛЕВЫХ ОКСИГИДРАТОВ

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Аннотация: В работе сделаны далеко идущие предположения о квантово-коллоидном представлении материи как **МАКРОСИСТЕМЫ**: микроскопическая запутанная система становится граничной макроскопической (например) оксигидратной системой, то есть особой квантовой формой сложных соотношений, т.е. электромагнитные шумы запутанные состояния (entangledstates) кластерных коллоидных систем.

Запутанность оксигидратных систем представляет собой особую квантовую форму корреляций составных систем, не имеющую классического аналога. оно возникает в системе, состоящей из двух и более взаимодействующих подсистем (или взаимодействовавших ранее, а затем отделившихся), и представляет собой суперпозицию макроскопически различных состояний. В этом случае колебания отдельных частей связаны между собой, но не классическими взаимодействиями (корреляциями), а нелокальными квантовыми корреляциями.

Предложен экспериментальный метод оценки размеров третьих кластеров оксигидратных систем в дисперсионной среде с учетом запутанности как особой квантовой формы корреляций составных систем, не имеющий классического аналога. Оно возникает в системе, состоящей из двух и более взаимодействующих подсистем, и представляет собой суперпозицию макроскопически различных состояний. В этом случае колебания отдельных частей связаны между

собой, но не классическими взаимодействиями (корреляциями), а нелокальными квантовыми корреляциями.

Ключевые слова: лагранжевы карты, оксигидратные системы, коллоидные кластеры, спонтанный пульсационный ток, спайковый выброс, диффузный двойной электрический слой, диссоциационное непропорциональное разрушение макромолекул, теория Уитни, геометрия каустик

Introduction.

Advancements in postclassical physics make it possible to apply its major attainments in colloid systems to consideration and research of the subtlest properties, e.g., of surfaces and catalysis. The specifics of postclassical physics worth highlighting are as follows.

1. In postclassical physics, reality is founded on the concept of causal connections. Postclassical physics discovered the idea of quantum correlation. Causal connections are a property of a model, not of global experience. The very notion of causal connections only makes sense within a theory that retains logical relations between elements. On the other hand, any human experience uninterpretable by any theory indicates that there is a correlation between an event that corresponds to A and an event that corresponds to [3].

2. To describe the physical state of a body, a motion equation for the function $\psi(x, y, z, t)$ is to be found, which we will refer to as the wave function, as Alexander Alexandrov first did in 1934. As a result, a mechanics will be built, which is only differs from the classical mechanics in a description of a physical state of a body by the wave function introduced, and based on the Schrödinger equation

$$m \frac{d^2 \vec{r}}{dt} = \nabla U$$

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} = \left(\frac{1}{2m} \hat{p}^2 + U \right) \psi$$

instead of the Newton equations of motion for a material point.

The above suggests that quantum mechanics cannot be regarded as microworld mechanics only; quantum mechanics is a more perfect version

of classical mechanics, able, however, to describe both microworld and macroworld phenomena.

3. Here, manifestations of special macroscopic quantum effects are to be found.

Macroscopic quantum effects is an aggregate of phenomena in which characteristic features of quantum mechanics immediately manifest themselves in behaviors of macroscopic objects. As a general rule, macroscopic objects here contain great amounts of atoms, which is described by classical physical equations to a high accuracy, exclusive of the Planck constant \hbar – a constant characteristic of quantum physics.

The set of macroscopic quantum physical effects is rather wide, and ranges from conventional thermal radiation to the photoelectric effect, the operation of optical quantum generator – laser, radioactivity, superfluid helium-4, superconductivity in metals, synchrotron radiation effects, low-temperature tunneling reactions, the discrete quantum Hall effect, and macroscopic quantum coherent effects induced by non-stationary magnetic field as part the dynamics of high-spin magnetic nanoclusters.

As quantum cybernetics evolved, the manifestations of quantum teleportation and quantum correlation effects were discovered.

4. Non-physical macroscopic quantum effects. According to Penrose and Hameroff, the human brain is a quantum system, and a quantum computer is a computational device that uses functional properties implementing quantum algorithms of the human brain.

5. Einstein, Podolsky, and Rosen first demonstrated a quantum paradox, the EPR paradox, that lead to the discovery of distant connections between quantum objects, which are now referred to as quantum correlations. From relativistic physical perspective, a connection at a distance is a non-physical connection that cannot exist in nature. Yet, experiments have proved that the connections in question do exist. The application effect discovered by us in 196 [1, 2] was important here as well: two particles described by a shared wave function (a quantum correlation) keep interaction even if are at a considerable distance, but the interaction in question is non-classical and non-force interaction. The underlying cause of the connection is trivial – the interacting particles have a shared wave function, which is a firmly established fact.

6. Timelessness of quantum correlations. Quantum correlations are instantaneous and out-of-time. In case of a macroscopic quantum

correlation, a specific act at one space point immediately causes a response at a distant one.

7. What shape is the Universe as it is being formed? A historical era α is a mode, u_α – a complex-valued wave within the configurative superspace that is a product of the superspace of Wheeler 3D geometries, the physical matter, the ethnosphere, the biosphere, the sociosphere, and the noosphere. A historical era does not include time, as a historical era is a “frozen state”, but it includes knowledge of the space geometry 3Q , the matter μ , the environment state B , the ethnical field state e , the social field state σ , and the noospheric field state ν . Therefore, $u_\alpha = \psi_\alpha({}^3Q, \mu, B, e, \sigma, \nu)$.

Linear ordered reality that is the sums of historical eras – waves is

$$\psi = c_\alpha u_\alpha + c_\beta u_\beta + \dots$$

The function ψ satisfies to the Wheeler-DeWitt equation

$$\left[G_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} \varepsilon \frac{\delta}{\delta h_{\alpha\beta}} \frac{\delta}{\delta h_{\gamma\delta}} + \sqrt{\hbar} {}^{(3)}R + \varepsilon(h_{\alpha\beta}, \mu, B, e, \sigma, \nu) \right] \psi({}^{(3)}Q, \mu, B, e, \sigma, \nu)$$

The Wheeler-DeWitt allows to describe the birth of the four-dimensional spacetime.

The equation contains the term $\varepsilon(h_{\alpha\beta}, \mu, B, e, \sigma, \nu)$ that takes into account the contribution from the material sources μ , the environment B , and the fields e, σ, ν .

In quasi-classical approximation, at which one inevitably arrives as a certain human consciousness condition, the wave function

$$\psi_\alpha({}^{(3)}Q, \mu, B, e, \sigma, \nu) = (\text{slow-changing amplitude function}) e^{-\frac{i}{\hbar} S_\alpha({}^{(3)}Q, \mu, B, e, \sigma, \nu)}$$

corresponds to each historical era α .

And the wave packet

$$\psi_{\alpha}^{(3)}(Q, \mu, B, e, \sigma, \nu) = c_{\alpha} \psi_{\alpha}^{(3)}(Q, \mu, B, e, \sigma, \nu) + c_{\beta} \psi_{\beta}^{(3)}(Q, \mu, B, e, \sigma, \nu) + \dots$$

corresponds to all historical era types, that is, to the whole of collective consciousness.

Wherever phases of specific historical era consciousnesses α, β, \dots coincide, that is,

$$S_{\alpha}^{(3)}(Q, \mu, B, e, \sigma, \nu) = S_{\beta}^{(3)}(Q, \mu, B, e, \sigma, \nu)$$

constructive interference occurs, leading to the birth of a historical sequence common for all historical eras – that is, space-time reality.

8. PATTERNS: What pattern does the Universe follow?

A pattern is a regularity in objects, natural and societal phenomena. As of now, there is no answer to the above question yet. Reality is not composed of particles of matter in the course of evolution from the past to the future, but it appear in its entirety from the past to the future while following set patterns, that is, specific patterns. This is how the quantum theory defines patterns.

Electromagnetic Noise Entangled States Of Cluster Colloid Systems.

Summary.

In this work, we have made far-reaching assumptions concerning quantum colloid concept of a substance as a macrosystem that a microscopic entangled system transits into a boundary macroscopic oxyhydrate system, that is, a special quantum form of composite correlations between electromagnetic noise entangled states of cluster colloid systems.

Preface.

As Stephen Hawking wrote in his Brief History of Time, “In general, quantum mechanics does not predict a single definite result for an observation.” By contrast, quantum mechanics presupposes a series of dissimilar results and gives probabilistic assessment for each of those results. This means that the same measurement made for many similar systems, their initial conditions being the same, may give result A in one case, result B in another case, and so on, and so forth. One can count how many cases give the result is A or B, but cannot predict the result of each

specific measurement. This means that quantum mechanics is about certain amounts of inevitable unpredictability.

Quantum mechanics is founded on Heisenberg Uncertainty Principle and Pauli Exclusion Principle, and stemmed from wave-particle duality, where particles are considered either waves or particles, as applies. Thus, we arrive at a very important conclusion that interference is necessarily observed in such systems, with the crest of one wave overlapping the trough of the other, and the waves damping each other.

Quantum chemical principle hold true for elementary particles, e.g., a proton, with dimensions 0.5 to 0.86 femtometer, the dimensions being one million times less than a nanometer. Genuine wave-particle duality was established for those particles.

Researchers tend to overlook intermediary and more sizable substance particles, and their wave properties, though the subject is the domain of colloid chemistry (CC) and its subdivision of nanocluster (or ultradisperse) states.

Stéphane Leduc [5], F.M. Shemyakin, and P.F. Mikhalev [4] pioneered the subject, the works by Leduc dating back to 1910, and it was in 1910 when Stéphane Leduc came forward with the idea that periodic reactions could be some sort of wave processes that should be considered with diffusion of colloid particles taken into account, not just in terms of pure wave phenomena. Leduc wrote that wave concepts had prevailed because of the resonant controversy between Sir Isaac Newton and Christiaan Huygens about the nature of light. Later on, researchers never faced any other phenomena where emission of particles combined came hand in hand with wave processes. However, it is periodic reactions that combine emission (Newtonian) processes and wave processes, that is, emission processes form periodic waves that diffract and interfere in accordance with Huygens' ideas, the concept that had been first formulated by Leduc fourteen years before Louis de Broglie laid the basis for wave mechanism. Of course, the concept confused phenomena that existed at various levels.

In the 1930s, F.M. Shemyakin and P.F. Mikhalev endeavored to generalize those wave concepts for various colloid chemical objects [4]. But it was not until the 1950s and the 1960s that Belousov and Zhabotinsky published their collaborative articles (Belousov-Zhabotinsky reaction) that were in a different league from the mainstream research of that time, which

was quite expectable, as chemical industries of the time were required to yield products with definitely predictable properties, that is, premium quality products, and the researchers fell in with the requirement, except for Zhabotinsky et al.

Emission wave duality of behavior of periodic processes in oxyhydrates of *d*- and *f*-element

So, it was between 1910 and 1930 when a number of scholars, namely, Stéphane Leduc [5], F. Shemyakin, and P. Mikhalyov [4], put forward the tenets of the emission-wave theory of periodical processes in colloid systems, including oxyhydrate systems. There were a number of works on wave properties and Belousov-Zhabotinsky reactions, which dealt with the selfsame behavioral duality in oxyhydrate systems. However, as we proved in [6-9], it was through nonlinear wave properties of those systems that one could reveal and understand a great number of interesting colloid chemical phenomena in coordination oxo-ol compounds, that is, in terms of the emission wave theory of periodical processes. In fact, this article justifies the approach.

The principal mathematical formula of the emission wave theory will be the expression (which is practically similar to de Broglie equation for the microworld)

$$\lambda \cdot v = \text{const},$$

that is the product of distance between the adjacent maximums of the wave process (λ) multiplied by the propagation velocity of the diffusion field (v) is a constant value. This value is called the periodicity constant. The expression for the diffusion flux vector and the velocity vector shows that

$$\Delta \bar{x} \cdot \Delta \bar{v} \geq D.$$

The pulsation oscillation of the ionic flows put forward by us in [9, 10], are therefore expected to take place in the vicinity of a constant diffusion coefficient the quantitative evaluation of which was provided in [11]. Described below are a number of results of a great significance that furnish an irrefutable proof of the duality of the emission-wave behavior of oxyhydrate colloid chemical systems.

Natural or forced periodic action of molecular surroundings of a cluster, which render it into a periodic oscillatory state, account for the observable wave properties of the disperse medium – nanoclusters.

It is fair to notice here that those periodic systems can be understood if considered in terms of quantization, an idea that may appear as sheer madness, unless we take into account a property of quantum systems, called “entangled states” [12-14].

“Entangled states” and “spooky actions at a distance” had been ignored for decades until John Bell took interest in them. Inspired by David Bohm’s ideas [15] (de Broglie-Bohm theory), Bell proposed analysis of the EPR paradox (Einstein, Podolsky, Rosen paradox), and, in 1964, formulated the inequalities that laid foundation for further physical experiments.

Finally, classical experiments conducted by Alain Aspect in 1981 [15, 16] clearly proved that Einstein’s local realism did not exist. Once a thought experiment, “spooky actions at a distance” became physical reality.

Entanglement as a quantum mechanical phenomenon means appropriate correlation between two or more particles, with the correlation retained even if the particles are remote beyond any other known interactions of whatever kind, be it electrical, electromagnetic interactions, or other. In other words, entanglement means correlation, interrelation, and interdependence, not confusion or a muddle [12, 14]. Entanglement is a special quantum form of correlation between compound systems, which has no classical analog, and forms in a compound system that consists of two or more interacting systems (or those that had interacted and then were separated), and is a superposition of macroscopically dissimilar states. Fluctuations in individual parts are interrelated through non-local quantum correlations, not through classical correlations. The essence of those quantum correlations in macrosystems remains unclear and we, colloid chemists, are to shed light on the phenomenon in terms of our systems.

Purely theoretical research into quantum correlations suggests [14] that the phenomenon ought to take place on the boundary of an entangled quantum system with a macroscopic entangled system phase boundary, or on a boundary of microscopic entangled system with a boundary macroscopic system, and ought to be decoherence at the output, that is, a transition of a quantum system into a microscopic state, while a reverse process of recoherence, that is, restoration of coherence, ought to evolve from a macroscopic boundary system at the input of an entangled state and further on to a macroscopic system at the output. The very presence of

quantum correlation boundaries is essential, and so is the fact that they exist as macroscopic objects, that is, the macroworld.

B.B. Kadomtsev [17] once expressed an exciting idea that threads of quantum correlations could be possibly running through the entire external world. Therefore, quantum correlations (and, consequently, the very entanglement) are a phenomenon that lies beyond the limits of classical quantum mechanics.

Macroscopic phase boundary is exceptionally complex in colloid systems. Let us consider exposure of gel system 0 to light. Let there be light falling on an oxyhydrate gel, in which self-organization processes are in progress. It is our task to find what absorption occurs in the gel, and what the action of the light on the gel is. Let us assume that there is a beam of light with an electric field $\vec{E} = \{E_0 \sin \omega t, -E_0 \cos \omega t\}$ falling on the gel.

Polarization \vec{P} occurs in the gel. The equation for polarization dynamics in the absence of light is written down as

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \vec{P} = \Delta \vec{P} + \Omega[\vec{P}] + L[n]\vec{P} \quad (1)$$

where $L[n]$ is the gel density Liesegang operator, and $\Omega[\vec{P}]$ is the rotation operator.

Let us neglect the expression that contains the Liesegang operator, because the expression in question makes a relatively small contribution to the ratio, compared to the resonance of the external electromagnetic field and the proper rotation of the gel.

We will consider that any aftereffects (a kind of hysteresis) are caused by Fredericks effect and therefore can be described as Fredericks effect

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = E_0^2 (1 - 2u^2 / 3)u + K \Delta u \quad (2)$$

where K is a constant value, and E_0 is the strength of the external field.

It is desirable that we consider the director a vector value. We will approximately consider that the direction of the director coincides with that of the vector field, and assume that $|u| = |\vec{P}|$. From ratio

$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = E_0^2(1 - 2u^2/3)u + K\Delta u$, we extract a vector ratio for polarization vector deformation by the external field

$$\frac{\partial \vec{P}}{\partial t} = E_0^2(1 - 2\vec{P}^2/3)\vec{P} + K\Delta \vec{P} \tag{3}$$

Adding the external field and the rotation operator to the ratio, we obtain a system of equations

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial P_x}{\partial t} = E_0^2 \left(1 - \frac{2}{3}\vec{P}^2\right) P_x - P_y\Omega + D\Delta P_x + \omega E_0 \cos \omega t \\ \frac{\partial P_y}{\partial t} = E_0^2 \left(1 - \frac{2}{3}\vec{P}^2\right) P_y + P_x\Omega + D\Delta P_y - \omega E_0 \sin \omega t \end{cases} \tag{4}$$

To solve the ratio obtained, let us consider a specific case, in which we neglect the values of the form $E_0^2 P_x + D\Delta P_x$ and $E_0^2 P_y + D\Delta P_y$. Let us find solutions in the form $P_x = A \cos \Omega t$, $P_y = A \sin \Omega t$. In a case when the situation is far from resonance, we can neglect the external field. As a result, we obtain for A an equation: $A' = -\frac{2}{3} E_0^2 A^3$. This equation is easy

to solve, and the specific solution is $A = \frac{1}{E_0 \sqrt{t}}$.

The final solution is $P_x = \frac{\cos(\Omega t)}{\sqrt{t}}$, $P_y = \frac{\sin(\Omega t)}{\sqrt{t}}$. Adding the amplitudes and calculating the spectral transformation $I = \frac{1}{E_0} \int_0^T \frac{\cos \omega t}{\sqrt{t}}$, we

find that $I = C_s \frac{FresC\left(\sqrt{\frac{\omega T}{2}}\right)}{\sqrt{\omega}}$, where $FresC(x)$ is Fresnel cosine integral.

The spectrum near the resonance is shown on Figure 1.

Figure 1 – The intensity of light passed through gel against frequency, I is relative intensity, ω is frequency

The spectrum near the resonance. Line 3 is $T = 1$, line 2 is 10, line 1 is 50. all the other constants were taken for 1. There are many periods in reality, and near the resonance
$$I = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\omega - \Omega}}$$
.

A mesophase-like cholesteric gel samples lose their helical textures when subjected to long isothermal drying, and transit into homeotropic (or a similar) structure [18, p. 213] when exposed to electromagnetic emission, that is, their structures become ordered and banded, though the transition takes longer in the latter case. Somewhat similar processes are observed in mobile organic liquid crystals. In this case, confocal structures transit into fingerprint textures in an electrical field positioned perpendicular to the bearing surfaces.

A direct transition from this texture to homeotropic one is a regular Fredericks transition for liquid crystals [18, c. 213]. In case of oxyhydrate systems, a similar effect is produced by spontaneous structuring in a “slowed down” gel system. In other words, exposure to electromagnetic field is indirectly substituted with exposure to flexoelectric effect that produces the same result [19].

We have found through experiment that a gel transforms from a selectively dissipative into a transparent one. Destruction of the original chiral smectic structure can be observed when the gel is exposed to electromagnetic emission, namely, the near ultraviolet that is softer. As a

result, gel samples assume higher sorptive capacity caused by unwinding (or destruction) of chiral smectic formations and transition of the gel into a homeotropic-like state. Prior to exposure, the gels were sorptive inactive. Those states are also optically transparent after an exposure, see Figure 2.

Figure 2 – Absorption spectra of yttrium oxyhydrate

This transition of gel phase is reversible and periodically recurrent whenever incident light wavelength changes. We have highlighted this effect to prove that textural differentiation is essential to gel phase of a substance.

The effect of formation of smectic type helical structures also accounts for tinting of yttrium oxyhydrate gels, which we considered in one of our earlier work [20]. In the latter case, optical effect manifests itself in wavelength shift of selective diffraction reflection towards higher wavelengths (so-called red shift), which was mentioned in [21], while decrease in the helix pitch (self-organization) is accompanied by a shift of the tinting towards shorter wavelengths (blue shift). Both are limit cases for our system as well.

Samples were synthesized at pH 9.27; yttrium content was 0.080 moles per sample; synthesizes time was 2 hours; spectra 1, 2, and 3 were recorded with a 30-minute span.

As it was demonstrated in [21, 22], certain oxo-ol chemical reactions occur in this case, and those reactions may create either stable or metastable molecular formations in the oxyhydrate, and those formations are also tinted. Sometimes, it is rather hard to tell between tinting caused by liquid crystalline nature of a gel (diffraction scattering) and that caused by quantum processes, that is, electronic transitions. Works [22, 23] prove that

causes behind tinting of yttrium oxyhydrate samples are of electronic nature, caused by formation of certain unstable transitional states, absorption spectra of which are observed within the visible spectrum as well.

Luminescence effects are characteristic of mesophase-like systems. The effects in questions may be largely attributed to electronic structural activity that occurs in a gel and triggers the above-mentioned electronic transitions. While yttrium oxyhydrate samples are not luminescent, yttrium oxyhydrate gels that are systems containing bound water, do demonstrate luminescence. Though the property in question is not apparently general, yet it can be considered a specific case. Luminescence may be generated by, e.g., chiral groups of yttrium oxyhydrate molecules.

Therefore, a microscopically entangled system adjacent to a macroscopical oxyhydrate system is a special quantum form of composite correlations between electromagnetic noise entangled states of cluster colloid systems, which we considered earlier.

It is worth mentioning that the entangled state is currently understood and interpreted rather broadly and pluralistically [14]. E.g., researchers [24] believe that quantum entanglement is just another name for “uncertainty principle” or “superposition” etc. Quantum mechanics knows three principal states of quantum systems, namely, pure states, mixed states, and eigenstates. A pure state is a state described by a wave functions or a superposition of wave functions. Eigenvalues of operators that describe those states are called quantum numbers.

Nonetheless, quantum mechanics knows states that cannot be described by wave functions. Those are mixed states. Unlike pure states, they are described not by wave functions but by a density matrix called statistical operator that only assesses probabilities W_1, W_2 of finding a system in any of the quantum state described by wave functions. This is exactly what Stephen Hawking says.

It is worth noting that quantum states do not interfere when in mixed states in contrast to superpositions of pure states, e.g., in an unpolarized particle beam.

The concept of quantum correlation is the key to understanding entangled states. Entangled states are defined as those of quantum correlation. Quantum correlations or entangled states may emerge in a system that consists of two or more interacting subsystems, which means

that entanglement is just a quantum form of correlations. However, one should bear in mind that there are two types of correlations, namely, quantum (or microscopic) and classical (macroscopic) correlations.

This is a characteristic of electromagnetic noise entangled states of cluster colloid systems, for those are not microscopic, but macroscopic systems.

Traditional sources of entangled states are cascade decay of atomic excitations and spontaneous parametrical scattering of electromagnetic fields (e.g., light) in nonlinear systems. Those processes are harnessed to create photon pairs with entangled states of polarization, later to be controlled by means of simplest linear optical devices, e.g., mirrors and polarizing prisms. Thus created, photon pairs propagate at the speed of light, making it hard to localize and to keep them for further use, and this is where the principal disadvantage of such sources of entangled states lies.

We have proved [6] that entanglement of a quantum colloid gel macrosystem should be expressed through a wave equation (Liesegang operator) that describes tri-particle interactions cluster interactions in the system [4-8], when a superpositional formation of gel phase by some third dissipative clusters formed by recordable current surges of active particles is observed. Giant clusters of bound (hydrate) water that facilitates superpositional formations, are inextricable parts of disperse aqueous media. It is appropriate to say that a spatial cluster discretization or a spatial form of cluster entanglement take place there. Then, “spooky actions at a distance” become of a cyclical or wave nature, and become confined to a quite explainable space. Modeling of superpositional formation of such a gel entanglement in an active electromagnetically excited medium was described in our monograph [8]. Now it would be necessary to make far-reaching assumptions concerning the quantum colloid concept of a substance as a macrosystem.

Physics in general and theoretical physics in particular have been placing special emphasis on entanglement, especially in the recent years [12, 17]. Published in 1938, a monograph by M. F. Shemyakin and P. F. Mikhalev entitled “Physicochemical periodic processes” generalized extensive experimental material from more than one thousand sources and led us, present-day readers, to quantum colloid understanding of the substance. Seeing as the very formation of quantum mechanics was through its final stage and was limited to describing behaviors of elementary

particles in the 1930s, it would be decades before the concept of universal entanglement would emerge; this was why the ideas presented by M. F. Shemyakin and P.F. Mikhalev in their monograph got no support from universities, and the monograph passes unnoticed. Thus, the concept of entanglement in macrosystems was pioneered – indirectly – by prominent colloid chemists, namely, Raphael Eduard Liesegang, M. F. Shemyakin, P. F. Mikhalev, Stéphane Leduc, just to name a few. To the best of our ability, we are going to elaborate on those concepts [6-10].

Optical properties of gel oxyhydrates and gel clusters; oxyhydrate electromagnetic “noise”

In this section of our article, we have attempted to calculate sizes of nanocluster particles that form gel cluster structures, against the background of periodic electromagnetic noise. Let us relate those measurements to Liesegang operator for third lightweight clusters in tri-particle interaction in gel phase. Let us consider the principal patterns of the quantum mechanical concept of the substance as a macrosystem.

We introduced the Liesegang operator for cluster particles of colloid systems that contain electronic entanglement, contrary to the Schroedinger equation for wave femtometers of dimensional elementary particles [16], which show this entanglement. Let us assume by definition that the strongly nonlinear equation below for colloid chemical systems is the general solution to the Liesegang equation [10].

$$\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} - D \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \right) n = m,$$

where n and m are values that are physically an “action” of a cluster particle, which is written down as

$$n = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} a_k \cos \omega_k \Phi + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} b_k \sin \omega_k \Phi, \quad m = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} A_k \cos \omega_k \Phi + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} B_k \sin \omega_k \Phi$$

The “action,” however, can be written down as Lagrangian, as shown below

$$S = \int_{t_1}^{t_2} L(x_i, v_i) dt$$

where S is the action.

Abstract suggests that the above concerns the solution to the problem that containing the Liesegang operator and has a form $\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} + L[u]$, the solution, according to [25,26], is function $u(x, t)$.

This function, $u(x, t)$, is continuous everywhere at $0 \leq t \leq T$ and meets an equation $\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} + L[u]$.

Hence, it is easy to deduce that

$$L[u] \cong S = \int_{t_1}^{t_2} L(x_i, v_i) dt, \quad \cong 1/n \int_{t_1}^{t_2} L(x_i, v_i) dt,$$

which means that Liesegang operator is a Lagrangian for pulsation cluster phenomena.

According to [24], the Liesegang operator can be set as described below.

Definition. Let $a < b$ are two fixed numbers. Then, we will refer to an operator that puts function $g=(x, t)$ [$u(x, t)$] in correspondence to function $u(x, t)$ as Liesegang operator $[u]$. Continuous functions $u(x, t)$, $x \in R^1$, $t \geq 0$, such that $a \leq u(x, t) \leq b$ are the definition range of the Liesegang operator.

– $g(x, t) = +\alpha \cdot u(x, t)$, $\alpha = const > 0$ either if function $u(x, \tau) < b$ for all $\tau < t$, or, if $\exists \bar{\tau} < t$, such that $u(x, \bar{\tau}) = a$, and $a < u(x, \tau) < b$ for all τ , such that $\bar{\tau} < \tau < t$;

– $g(x, t) = -\alpha \cdot u(x, t)$, $\alpha = const > 0$ if function $u(x, \bar{\tau}) = b$ and $a < u(x, \tau) < b$ for all τ , such that $\bar{\tau} < \tau < t$.

As for the solution to the problem containing the Liesegang operator, which has the form

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} + L[u],$$

the solution to it, according to [26], is function

$u(x, t)$, that belongs to the class described above and, in addition to that, meets two more conditions:

– it is equal to the given function $\varphi(x)$, that sets the initial distribution, that is $u(0, x) = \varphi(x)$;

– there exists a finite number of continuous curves $s_k = \{(x, t) : x = \sigma_k(t), 0 \leq c_k \leq t \leq d_k\}$, where various curves may have shared points at their ends only at $t = c_k$ or $t = d_k$, we should point out that for unlimited time, the number of those curves is also infinitely great within an unlimited region;

– function $u(x, t)$ is continuous everywhere if $0 \leq t \leq T$ and meets equation $\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} + L[u]$ everywhere at $0 \leq t \leq T$ beyond curves s_k ;

– function $u(x, t)$ has one-sided derivatives $\frac{\partial u}{\partial x}$ on curves s_k ,

$L[u]$ change signs, depending on which side of curve s_k is at $c_k < t < d_k$

It is obvious that the problem constructed falls into a series of well-known Florin problems.

We propose the following experimental method for assessment of sizes of third clusters in a disperse medium, with entanglement taken into account [10, 27] as a special quantum form of correlation between compound systems, and having no classical analogue. Entanglement emerges in a system that consists of two or more interacting subsystems that a superposition of macroscopically dissimilar states, where fluctuations of individual parts are interconnected through non-local quantum correlations, not through classical interactions (correlations).

Equation for light absorption by conformer “light” clusters.

The optical density behaves unusually in gel oxyhydrate systems of d- and f- elements [8, 10, 27] changing in a complex, almost a wave-like periodical way. The question then arises what are the reasons behind those changes and how they correlate with the subject matter of this book.

We believe that it is the internal noise produced by a gel oxyhydrate system that defines its optical properties.

The cluster noise atmosphere of a colloid chemical system is directly connected to the macromolecular structure of the residue, or rather

it is defined by it. Conducting research into structures of oxyhydrate gels means conducting research into the mechanisms behind synchronization of those stochastic systems, that is, to find out how the noise affects, e.g., the optical properties, the sorptive properties, etc. [6-10, 27].

We are going to proceed from the idea that electromagnetic emission (light) is absorbed by gel phase. In addition, let us make an assumption that the absorption coefficient of a noisy gel is $\gamma = \xi + i\sigma$, where ξ is the absorption coefficient's real part, and σ is the complex part that causes the absorption of light by the matter.

Then the Helmholtz equation for the transition of light through the gel will assume the form

$$\Delta \vec{E} + k^2 \vec{E} = 0$$

with a condition added that the solution tends to zero on the infinity. The notations used herein are: \mathbf{k} is the wave vector, and \vec{E} is the electric field.

Figure 3 – The region where the problem for the light absorption by a gel can be solved

Let us find out how the wave vector depends on the parameters of the matter being studied. It is commonly believed that $k^2 = \frac{\omega^2}{c^2} \epsilon \epsilon_0 \mu$, where

$\epsilon\epsilon_0$ is for the permittivity, and μ is for the magnetic permeability. It is commonly thought that magnetic permeability exerts little influence on the changes occurring in a magnetic field, since the magnetic field of an electromagnetic wave is weak. Let us assume that it is really weak, and, therefore assume the magnetic permeability as equal to zero. As for the permittivity, according to the definition, the matter contains $\vec{E} = \epsilon\vec{P}$, where \vec{P} is for the medium's polarization vector. At first, we will choose the simplest way to go and assume that $\epsilon = \xi + i\sigma$ in terms of the notations above. In other words, we think that light is absorbed by oxyhydrate's gel phase, but we are not going to take into consideration the secondary consequences of that absorption. It is natural, however, that those interactions are notable, they have been studied by us and described in detail in [6-8] and are partially considered above.

In this case, we have to consider a boundary value problem for passing of light through a gel, which is shown on Figure 3 above:

1. Let us assume that there is one boundary condition stipulated at the wall while the a condition for the transmitted light is stipulated at the wall $z = L$. The trouble is that we do not know the latter condition.

2. Everywhere in the region $0 < z < L$, the wave vector is defined as $k^2 = \frac{\omega^2}{c^2}(\xi + i\sigma)$.

3. Everywhere outside the region $0 < z < L$ (hereinafter referred to as region B), the wave vector is defined by the relation $k^2 = \frac{\omega^2}{c^2}$.

All in all, the problem looks like as shown below

$$\begin{cases} \Delta\vec{E} + k^2\vec{E} = 0, & k^2 = \frac{\omega^2}{c^2} \begin{cases} 1, & z \geq L \\ \xi + i\sigma, & 0 \leq z \leq L \end{cases} \\ \vec{E}|_{z=0} = \vec{E}_0(x, y, t) \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

where $\vec{E}_0(x, y, t)$ is a value of the incident electric field at the region's boundary, and the t value is the time that will act as a parameter in our problem.

For the purposes of further calculations, it is convenient to believe that among all the field vectors, only the OZ axis field remains, seeing as the gel is formed by extended macromolecules. The rest of the fields can be assumed as being equal to E_z , while assuming the field to be polarized in a circular fashion, or even totally neglecting it.

Plane wave expansion

Let us study the properties of light absorption through a square with a side $L_x = L_y$. Let us assume that the field is equal to zero on the square's edges ($x = 0, x = L_x, y = 0, y = L_y$). In this case, we will seek the solution among the problem's cross-section eigenfunctions, in other words, we are going to seek the E_z that looks like:

$$E_z = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} E_{nm}(z, t) \sin\left(\frac{\pi n x}{L_x}\right) \sin\left(\frac{\pi m y}{L_y}\right)$$

Note: the value E_{nm} is only slightly dependent on the square's cross-section at least among the first harmonics, which is why the dependence in question can be neglected.

For E_{nm} we obtain:

$$\frac{\partial^2 E_{nm}(z, t)}{\partial z^2} + \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \sum_{l=1}^{\infty} \alpha_{jnml} E_{jl}(z, t) = 0 \tag{6}$$

with the boundary conditions being:

$$E_{nm} \Big|_{z=L} = \frac{\partial E_{nm}}{\partial z} \Big|_{z=L} \frac{\sin(kL)}{k} \quad \text{и} \quad E_{nm} \Big|_{z=0} = E_{nm}^{(0)}$$

The α_{jnml} values can be calculated by the formulas

$$\alpha_{nlmj} = \int_0^{L_x} dx \int_0^{L_y} k^2(x, y, t) \sin\left(\frac{\pi n x}{L_x}\right) \sin\left(\frac{\pi l x}{L_x}\right) \sin\left(\frac{\pi j y}{L_y}\right) \sin\left(\frac{\pi m y}{L_y}\right) dy$$

A few specific cases

Let us consider a case when we are only interested in one harmonic, namely E_{11} . Then the problem (4) with boundary conditions assumes the form

$$\frac{\partial^2 E_{11}(z, t)}{\partial z^2} + \alpha_{1111} E_{11}(z, t) = 0$$

Its general solution looks like $C_1 \exp(i\sqrt{\alpha_{1111}}z) + C_2 \exp(-i\sqrt{\alpha_{1111}}z)$. Now let us do quantitative calculations of how much of the electromagnetic field is absorbed by the gel. It is worth noting that $\zeta = \sqrt{\alpha_{1111}} = \sqrt{\xi_{1111} + i\sigma_{1111}} = \chi + i\varpi$. Therefore, $e^{i\zeta L} = e^{i\chi L} e^{-\varpi L}$, $e^{-i\zeta L} = e^{-i\chi L} e^{+\varpi L}$. Doing calculations in a rough and approximate way $\chi \approx k$, $0 < \varpi \ll k$, then $h \approx -\exp(-2ikL) \frac{1 - \sin(kL)}{1 + \sin(kL)} \exp\left(2\frac{\varpi L}{k}\right)$, that is, the h value will be augmented $q^2 = e^{\frac{2\varpi L}{k}}$ times.

Further on, $E|_{z=L} = E_{11}^{(0)} \left(\frac{h}{1+h} e^{i\zeta L} + \frac{1}{1+h} e^{-i\zeta L} \right)$, that is, the q factor is derived in the following way: $E|_{z=L} = E_{11}^{(0)} \left(\frac{q}{1+q^2 h_0} e^{ikL} + \frac{q h_0}{1+q^2 h_0} e^{-ikL} \right)$. If the q is considerable, then the electric field can be roughly evaluated as $E_{11}|_{z=L} \approx \frac{E_{11}^{(0)}}{q}$.

Connection to Liesegang operator

Now, let $\xi, \sigma \sim n$, where n is for the current concentration of nanoclusters (i – nanoclusters, which means i – dimension nanoclusters) in the gel. Therefore, $q = \exp\left(\frac{\lambda L \sqrt{n}}{k}\right)$.

If the concentration changes in accordance the law defined by the Liesegang operator [25, 26], then the electric field transmitted will change in accordance with the law of its own, e.g., as shown on Figure 4 and 5.

Figure 4 – The Liesegang operator and its respective phase diagram of a transmitted electromagnetic wave. The Figure on the left shows the nanoclusters concentration changing in time. X axis shows time in dimensionless units, Y axis shows the dimensionless concentration defined by Liesegang operator. The Figure on the right is a phase diagram of an electrical field in a transmitted wave. X axis shows the electric field in dimensionless units

A common plane wave

Now let us consider a case when we are not going to divide a wave into separate harmonics. Instead, we are going assume that we are facing a common plane incident wave. In this case, the solution will only be changed where $\zeta = \lambda\sqrt{n}$, will be dependent on x, y, t as well.

Figure 5 – The Figure on the left is the dimensionless concentration against dimensionless time (its concentration value is different from that on Figure 2). The Figure on the right is the diagram of the concentration’s respective field in a transited wave. The X axis contains the very field, the Y axis is its coordinate derivative

$$E|_{z=L} = E_{11}^{(0)} \left(\frac{h}{1+h} e^{i\zeta L} + \frac{1}{1+h} e^{-i\zeta L} \right),$$

$$h = -\exp(-2i\zeta L) \frac{1 - \frac{\zeta}{k} \sin kL}{1 + \frac{\zeta}{k} \sin kL} \quad (7)$$

What we are interested in is the ratio between the intensity when it enters a gel medium's and the intensity when it leaves the gel's medium,

$p = \left(\frac{E_z|_{z=L}}{E_z|_{z=0}} \right)^2$. Taking into consideration the calculations done in the

previous paragraph, the ration can be evaluated as $p \approx \frac{1}{q^2} = e^{-2\frac{k\varpi}{L}\sqrt{n}}$. Note:

the intensity in question is rather well spread over the space, while we are interested in the integral of any of its regions, which means that the light transmission coefficient will look like:

$$p = \iint_D \exp\left(-2\frac{\varpi L\sqrt{n}}{k}\right) dx dy \quad (8)$$

The result will be the two diagrams below

Figure 6 – Concentration dependence of clusters on time for a simplest helix. The Figure on the left is the clusters' concentration's spatial pattern. X and Y axes show spatial coordinates, Z axis shows the concentration's value in dimensionless units. The Figure on the right shows the level lines for the Picture on the left

Figure 7 – Changes in the intensity of the field's waves that has just transited through an oxyhydrate's clusters in a space. The Figure on the left is the ratio of the intensity square of the field's wave that has transited through a gel to the field's intensity square prior to the transition through the gel, depending on the spatial coordinates. The Figure on the right shows the level lines for the Figure on the left

The way the pulsation noise or self-organizational current in a magnetic field affects optical parameters of yttrium oxyhydrate

Our earlier works [9, 28] suggest that yttrium oxyhydrate gels are mesophase-like systems that are capable of changing their optical and sorption parameters when exposed to an electromagnetic emission.

Let us consider how pulsation self-organization current (toroidal noise in oxyhydrate systems) in a magnetic fields [29-33] affects optical parameters of yttrium oxyhydrate. Optical experiments were carried out as yttrium oxyhydrate gel as through self-organization in a magnetic field, as described in [34, 35], and when the gels were being exposed to magnetic fields outside of the electrochemical cell [34].

Fresh yttrium oxyhydrate gel was placed into an electrochemical cell fitted with platinum electrodes, which was a hollow tube with the $d=50$ to 80 mm. Simultaneously, the gel was being exposed to a magnetic field with the intensity $H=600 \pm 52$ Oe or $H=900 \pm 52$ Oe.

Another portion of the fresh gel was placed into a pan and then exposed to a static magnetic field, with its magnetic induction lines being perpendicular to the sample's plane. The intensity of the plane magnetic

field was $H=980\pm 52$ Oe. The exposure time was also six hours. All the gel synthesis experiments were thermostated at 298K.

The result of the measurements taken was a whole series of dependence of the changes in the gel samples' optical density on the transmitting light wavelength for a fresh yttrium oxyhydrate gel, as well for a gel exposed to a magnetic field with the intensity of 980 ± 52 Oe and for a gel exposed to a pulsation self-organizational current in magnetic fields with the intensities of 600 Oe and 900 Oe.

Optical density kinetic curves for yttrium oxyhydrate gels

Obtained theoretically, periodical changes in ratio $(1/p)$, which is the intensity of an incident wave of the electromagnetic field against the intensity of a transmitted wave have been conformed by research into optical properties of gel oxyhydrate systems (Fig. 8).

We also studied the kinetic dependence $A = f(t)$, where A is for the gel's optical density, and t is for the exposure time (minutes). The optical density measurements were taken at a certain wavelength of the incident light during an hour ($\lambda=350$ for a fresh gel; $\lambda=310$ for a gel that had been exposed to a pulsation current in a magnetic field of $H= 900$ or 600 Oe; and $\lambda=320$ for a gel that had been exposed to a magnetic field of $H= 980 \pm 52$ Oe).

Figure 8 – Changes in intensity of incident wave of field against intensity of transmitted electromagnetic wave

Spectral kinetic curves for the yttrium oxyhydrate gels were obtained in the course of the experiment. All the absorption spectra obtained (Fig. 9, 10) demonstrated periodic oscillations in the optical density, both in fresh gels and in gels that had been exposed to magnetic fields of $H=900$ Oe, 600 Oe, and 980 Oe.

Those periodical changes in the optical density can be understood by resorting Liesegang evolution operator to analyze the kinetic curves of a noise-polluted gel systems of oxyhydrates [36-38]. We assume that the system has an absorption coefficient that looks like $(\gamma = \xi + i\sigma)$, where ξ is for the absorption coefficient's real part that describes the light absorption by dispersion phase molecules, and σ is for the complex component σ that defines the light's dispersion on the oxyhydrate systems' particles.

Figure 9 – Oscillatory kinetics of the optical density in yttrium oxyhydrate gels, synthesis pH being =8.00; $n=0.00135$ mole; $L=5$ cm; $T = 30$ C°; – a gel that was exposed to a pulsation electric current in a magnetic fields with an intensity of 900 Oe, $\square=310$; – a gel that was exposed to a magnetic fields with an intensity of 980 52 Θ , $\square=320$

Figure 10 – Oscillatory kinetics of the optical density in yttrium oxyhydrate gels, synthesis pH being =8.00; $n=0.00135$ mole; $L=5$ cm; $T = 30$ C°; – a gel that was exposed to a pulsation electric current in a magnetic fields with an intensity of 900 Oe, $\square=310$; – a gel that was exposed to a magnetic fields with an intensity of 980 52 Э, $\square=320$

Earlier in this article, we evaluated the p value that characterized the relation between the light beam's intensity when it entered the gel medium and its intensity when it left the medium as being $p = \exp(-2k\sqrt{nL\lambda})$, where L was the pan's length, k was the wave vector, n was the concentration, $k^2 = \frac{\omega^2}{c^2}(\xi + i\sigma)$, and λ was the proportionality coefficient $\lambda = \left| \text{Im}\sqrt{\xi + i\sigma} \right|$. This assessment was done on the provision that $\xi, \sigma \sim n$, where n is the current concentration of fragments (cluster units) in the gels, which changes in accordance with the law prescribed by the Liesegang operator.

The dependences derived through calculations $A=f(\lambda)$ were of periodical nature (Fig. 8) and corresponded to the experimentally derived kinetic dependences for yttrium oxyhydrate gel (Fig. 9, 10).

It appears that periodic influence of pulsation noise or self-organization current in magnetic field on singularities of optical parameters of yttrium oxyhydrate is very complex, for it sets certain limits of a macroscopic quantum system, and those limits are inputs and outputs of a microscopic entangled system on the boundary with a macroscopic quantum correlated state. In other words, decoherence phenomena occur at the output, that is, a transition of the quantum system into a microscopic state and then a reverse process of recoherence, namely, restoration of coherence (inseparability) at the input into an entangled state, and those processes are periodic.

The changes in the optical density's oscillation amplitude, which is shown on the kinetic curves (Fig. 9, 10) suggest that the formative process is of periodical continuous nature, and in general suggest that the oxyhydrate system is stochastic and self-organized, and is dependent on the medium's pH [39, 40]. The optical density oscillations shown represented by the curves reflect the oxo-olic conformer polymerization and destruction processes going on in the oxyhydrate's fragments, accompanied and assisted by a pulsation periodical rearrangements going on the their double electric layers. The process is referred to as gel's maturing and is accompanied by periodically alternated increases and decreases in the optical density when the wave reaches a certain length, which corresponds to periodical changes in the ratio between different polymerization degree clusters in an oxyhydrate matrix, and to changes in the helix pitch of those pacemakers (clusters).

The absorption of the A value increases when polymerization aggregation of clusters is in progress and predominates, and decreases when polymer fragments destroy. All in all, the kinetic curves representing changes in the optical density provide information about how intense structuring process going on in a gel are. A fully formed yttrium oxyhydrate gel consists of different size spiral-shaped ionic clusters that are also referred to as pacemakers, and unstructured gel aggregates. The latter are low-molecular polymer particles with no pronounced arrangement. Proceeding from that idea, each of the maximums on the light absorption curve correspond has its own respective dimension clusters. We mean to say by it that a pacemaker of a certain type is made up by homogenous structure-formative elements that have similar polymerization degrees. Longer or shorter oligomer chains included in the structures of ionic

clusters are displaced into the intermicelle medium. As the process goes on, there is an increase in the relief pattern of the absorption bands, their number being limited in the gels' spectra experimentally obtained.

It follows from the kinetic dependences (Fig. 9, 10) that a temporal evolution of a gel system demonstrates all the external features of chaotic behavior, with some stochastic ordering elements included.

While studying the optical properties of silicic acid gels, it was found through experiment that had been synthesized with various initial solutions' concentrations that there were absorption bands in the visible part of the spectrum, besides, periodical kinetic spectral curves characteristic of dynamical systems were obtained [41].

Let us consider the absorption spectra of silica gels, with the initial solutions' concentrations being the same and the pH values being varied. All of the spectra obtained (see Figure 11 a, b, and c) contain optical density maximums. It was found in all experimental series that the number of the maximums and the wavelengths of certain maximums were constant in time for all the silica gel samples that had been synthesized at various pH values, with their sodium metasilicate concentration being the same. The numeric values of the maximums and the wavelength maximum values for silica gels that were synthesized at a constant concentration of their initial solutions, while their pH were different, are in Table 1. It follows from the Table that as the pH increases, the number of the maximums and their positions remain constants, the measurement error being ± 2 nanometers.

As the matrix-formative element's concentration increases, the wavelengths' range widens, with pronounced absorption maximums in it. It is remarkable that as the concentration increases, there is a bathochromic shift of the highest absorption maximum.

All in all, the number of the maximums and their positions in the spectra do not depend on the pH values, but are defined by the silicon's concentration in the initial solutions.

Figure 11 – Absorption spectra in silica gels. Sodium metasilicate concentration 0.3 moles/liter; samples’ age 22 days:
 a) pH 3.5...4.5; b) pH 5.0...6.0; c) pH 6.5...7.5

To study $SiO_2 \cdot nH_2O$ gel samples, we obtained kinetic curves of dependence of changes in the optical density on the wavelengths where there are absorption maximums, or where are not any (see Figure 10 and 11). Those dependences are also of a pronounced periodical nature. There are optical density oscillation amplitudes on the maximal wavelengths that are much higher than that, which are found when studying absorption spectra in dynamics. In other words, we observe in fact a noise pedestal, whose physical nature was described in [42].

As it was in the case of yttrium oxyhydrates, the oscillatory nature of the optical density of $SiO_2 \cdot nH_2O$ gels can be understood by resorting to the evolution Liesegang operator.

The experimental ρ value was calculated by us for that purpose. Please refer to our work [38] where $p = f(t)$ computed periodical

oscillatory dependences were presented. Their nature is in perfect accord with the kinetic dependences experimentally obtained (Fig. 12 and 13).

Figure 12 – Optical density oscillations' kinetics in a silica gel synthesized at pH = 3.5; the initial concentration of sodium metasilicate = 0.3 moles/liter

Figure 13 – Optical density oscillations' kinetics in a silica gel synthesized at pH = 5.0; the initial concentration of sodium metasilicate = 0.3 moles/liter

The fact that the value of pH does not practically affect the number of absorption bands and their positions when the concentration of the initial solutions is the same (Fig. 11) is attributed to the presence of polymer clusters in the gel's matrix, which are both equally advantageous thermodynamically.

Similar results were obtained in the work on lanthanum oxyhydrates.

The optical density oscillations kinetic curves of silica gels (Fig. 12 and 13) curves 4 and 5 contain slight oscillatory changes that practically degenerate into straight lines. It is reasonable to interpret this fact as a stop in rounding of helical nanoclusters that form the gel lattice by the wave having the length > 334 nanometers. Any transition of electromagnetic waves through those clusters is normally defined by the periodical character of the relation $1/p$, see Figure 8, which is why it is through conducting consequential kinetic experiments that one can evaluate the maximum dimensions of the nanoclusters, which are recorded in the system for various wavelengths. The clusters' dimensions are < 334 nanometers in our case. Those data generally coincide both with those provided in literature [35]. It is natural that smaller dimensions clusters that cause a decrease in the system's optical density (absorption of the electromagnetic emission) are also included into this range.

It follows from Figure 13 that when the silica gel's pH is 5.0, the clusters' dimensions are supposed to increase due to polycondensation effect. It is not impossible to evaluate the lower limit of the cluster's dimensions. On Figure 12, that limit evaluatively ranges from 312 to 314 nanometers, when the clusters are yet to form and the optical density time curves are still linear.

Those facts are completely true for measurements taken in the optical density of yttrium oxyhydrate gels, shown on Pictures 9 and 10. In this case, when yttrium oxyhydrate's pH is 9.0, an observable oscillatory process occurs at wavelengths 310 and 320 nanometers. The wavelength of 350 nanometers forms interruptions in the optical density, all of them having A constant values. One can therefore assume that the clusters' maximum dimensions do not exceed 310-320 nanometers in this case. Larger clusters may also form over time. When pH is 8.0, the cluster's maximum dimensions are more heterogeneous, namely < 320 nanometers. The dimensional anisotropy increases when wavelengths are 350 and 310 nanometers, which becomes understandable, taking into consideration the increase in the polymerization as the pH in d-elements increases. The magnetic field's action also contributes to the process in this case. However, this method of assessment of cluster sizes is rather inaccurate until we assess the conditions for emission interference on oxyhydrate clusters.

The phenomenon of transition of the system to a state of inseparability or coherence can be proved by the interference approach to experimental estimation of average dimensions of ion clusters in oxyhydrate gels, which we proposed in [43].

Any manifestation of inseparability of a cluster colloid system, occurring in a colloid chemical cell, determined by its capability of interference or diffraction, is indicative of an entangled state of the cluster colloid system.

Conclusions:

1. Quantum mechanics cannot be regarded as microworld mechanics only; quantum mechanics is a more perfect version of classical mechanics, able, however, to describe both microworld and macroworld phenomena, where manifestations of special macroscopic quantum effects are to be found. Macroscopic quantum effects is an aggregate of phenomena in which characteristic features of quantum mechanics immediately manifest themselves in behaviors of macroscopic objects. As a general rule, macroscopic objects here contain great amounts of atoms, which is described by classical physical equations to a high accuracy, exclusive of the Planck constant \hbar – a constant characteristic of quantum physics. Oxyhydrate gels of d- and f-elements fall into the category.

2. In this work, far-reaching assumptions concerning Quantum colloid concept of a substance as a macrosystem that a microscopic entangled system transits into a boundary macroscopic oxyhydrate system, that is, a special quantum form of composite correlations between Electromagnetic noise entangled states electromagnetic noise entangled states of cluster colloid systems have been made.

3. Entanglement is a special quantum form of correlation between compound systems, which has no classical analog, and forms in a compound system that consists of two or more interacting systems (or those that had interacted and then were separated), and is a superposition of macroscopically dissimilar states, with fluctuations occurring in individual parts interrelated through non-local quantum correlations, not through classical correlations.

4. We propose the following experimental method for assessment of sizes of third clusters in a disperse medium, with entanglement taken into account as a special quantum form of correlation between compound systems, and having no classical analog. Entanglement emerges in a system

that consists of two or more interacting subsystems that a superposition of macroscopically dissimilar states, where fluctuations of individual parts are interconnected through non-local quantum correlations, not through classical interactions (correlations).

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